

Search for New Hypoglycemic Agents. Part III. Biguanide Derived from 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles and Thiazoles

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Several *N*-(5-alkyl or aryl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-yl)- and *N*-(4, 5-substituted-thiazol-2-yl)-biguanides have been synthesised to examine their hypoglycemic activity. A slight reduction in blood sugar level was observed when five of these compounds were screened on rats.

2-ARYLSULPHONAMIDO derivatives of 5-substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazole^{1,2} and 5-nitro thiazole³ have, recently, been found to display significant hypoglycemic activity. Some biguanide derivatives^{4,5,6} are also known to possess anti diabetic property. So, it was thought worthwhile to undertake the synthesis of title biguanides with the object to ascertain whether the presence of oxadiazole or thiazole nucleus in them could augment the hypoglycemic potency.

Hydrochloride of 2-amino-5-alkyl (or aryl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole or 2-amino-4,5-substituted thiazole was fused with dicyandiamide in the presence of a little water to yield the corresponding biguanide as hydrochloride.

Experimental

Melting points are not corrected.

2-Amino-4,5-substituted thiazoles were prepared according to the method of Dodson and King⁷.

2-Amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles :

These were synthesised from an aldehyde semicarbazone and sodium hypoiodite in accordance with a known procedure⁸.

N-(5-Alkyl or aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl) biguanides :

A mixture of 2-amino-5-alkyl or aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole hydrochloride (0.01 mol), dicyandiamide (0.01 mol) and water (0.5 ml) was heated in an oil bath at 130°-140° for 3 hr. On cooling the reaction mixture, a solid mass of biguanide hydrochloride was obtained. It was triturated with ether and crystallized from ethanol or isopropyl alcohol.

The properties and analytical data of the compounds thus prepared are summarized in Table 1.

N-(4,5-Substituted-thiazol-2-yl)biguanides :

These were prepared analogously from an appropriate thiazole hydrochloride and dicyandiamide.

TABLE I—*N*-(5-ALKYL OR ARYL-1, 3, 4-OXADIAZOL-2-YL) BIGUANIDE HYDROCHLORIDES

S.N.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen %	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	CH ₃	240-42	75	C ₅ H ₁₀ ON ₇ Cl	44.42	44.65
2.*	C ₆ H ₅	115	72	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ ON ₇ Cl	34.40	34.81
3.*	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	187	69	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₇ Cl	34.49	34.30
4.*	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	165	70	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ON ₇ Cl ₂	31.50	31.01
5.	C ₆ H ₅ CH = CH	212-13	65	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ ON ₇ Cl	31.51	31.87
6.	4-H ₃ CO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	197	67	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₇ Cl	31.00	31.46
7.	3-(H ₃ CO)-4-(HO)C ₆ H ₃	209	57	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₇ Cl	29.61	29.92
8.	3,4-(H ₃ CO) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	218-19	55	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₇ Cl	28.33	28.69

* Screened for hypoglycemic activity.

* For correspondence

TABLE 2—N-(4-5-SUBSTITUTED-THIAZOL-2-YL) BIGUANIDE HYDROCHLORIDES

S.N.	R ¹	R ²	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen %	
						Found	Calcd.
1.*	C ₆ H ₅	H	100	64	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₆ SCl	28.00	28.33
2.*	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	H	200-2	60	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ ON ₆ SCl	25.50	25.73
3.	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	H	214-15	53	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₆ SCl ₂	25.79	25.38
4.	<i>o</i> -HOC ₆ H ₄	H	217	57	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ON ₆ SCl	26.63	26.88
5.	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅ OOC	164	50	C ₉ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₆ SCl	27.77	27.41

* Screened for hypoglycemic activity

The biguanides formed as hydrochloride were re-crystallised from ethanol and are reported in Table 2.

Hypoglycemic Activity

The compounds no.'s 2, 3, and 4 (Table 1) and 1 and 2 (Table 2) were administered orally in rats at a single dose of 250 mg/kg body weight. All these compounds seemed to reduce blood sugar level in rats very slightly.

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